

Networking and rheology of concentrated clay suspensions “matured” in mineral medicinal water

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Abstract

This work studied the influence of “maturation” conditions (time and agitation) on aggregation states, gel structure and rheological behaviour of a special kind of pharmaceutical semisolid products made of concentrated clay suspensions in mineral medicinal water. Maturation of the samples was carried out in distilled and sulphated mineral medicinal water, both in static conditions (without agitation) and with manual stirring once a week, during a maximum period of three months. At the measured pH interval (7.5–8.0), three-dimensional band-type networks resulting from face/face contacts were predominant in the laminar (disc-like) clay suspensions, whereas the fibrous (rod-like) particles formed micro-aggregates by van der Waals attractions. The high concentration of solids in the studied systems greatly determined their behaviour. Rod-like sepiolite particles tend to align the major axis in aggregates promoted by low shearing maturation, whereas aggregates of disc-like smectite particles did not have a preferential orientation and their complete swelling required long maturation time, being independent of stirring. Maturation of both kinds of suspensions resulted in improved rheological properties. Laminar clay suspensions became more structured with time, independently from static or dynamic maturation conditions, whereas for fibrous clay periodic agitation was also required. Rheological properties of the studied systems have been related to aggregation states and networking mechanisms, depending on the type of clay minerals constituents. Physical stability of the suspensions was not impaired by the specific composition of the Graena medicinal water.

1. Introduction

Rheological properties of semisolid pharmaceutical products greatly determine their physical stability and applications (Lee et al., 2009). Clay minerals are prominent excipients used to achieve adequate semisolid formulations, having been the subject of numerous studies (Viseras et al., 2007). Peloids are special kind of health care semisolid systems consisting of a solid phase rich in clay minerals dispersed in mineral medicinal water. Pelotherapy, intended as the therapeutic use of naturally occurring sediments, is one of the most popular techniques in thermal treatments (Viseras and Cerezo, 2006). It consists in the local application of peloids for the treatment of musculoskeletal and skin diseases (Torresani, 1990; Fabiani et al., 1996; Sukenik et al., 1999; Argenziano et al., 2004; Cozzi et al., 2007; Fioravanti et al., 2007). In the last decade, beauty and anti-stress treatments were also added to these traditional uses (Morganti et al., 2001; Varvaresou et al., 2011). A very important aspect to consider in pelotherapy concerns on the need of peloids for specialized treatments. In fact, treatments with different purposes, such as traditional treatments (musculo-skeletal, rheumatic, skin) and cosmetic ones (beauty and anti-stress) should require the use of peloids with specific features suitable as appropriate. Therefore, formulation of exclusive peloids has been defined as the “new frontier” of pelotherapy (Veniale et al., 2007). For this purpose a systematic approach is needed, able to determine optimum characteristics of these special clay/water suspensions depending on the required treatment. This objective may be achieved studying not only the peloid itself, but also its components (mineromedicinal water and clay minerals) and the process of maturation (contact between the solid and water medium during a prolonged time period). For example, several studies have been published focusing on characteristics of peloids and their constituents, including mineralogical and chemical compositions (Summa and Tateo, 1998, 1999; Cara et al., 2000a; Sanchez et al., 2002; Veniale et al., 2004; Tateo et al., 2009; Baschini et al., 2010; Carretero et al., 2010; Karakaya et al., 2010; Rebelo et al., 2011a), thermal behaviour (Ferrand and Yvon, 1991; Cara et al., 2000b; Ortiz de Zárate et al., 2010; Casás et al., 2011; Knorst-Fouran et al., 2012) and biochemical and microbiological aspects (Andreoli and Rascio, 1975; Ferrara et al., 1999; Galzigna et al., 1996). Moreover, peloids are semisolid products that require a detailed

characterization of their rheological properties (Bettero et al., 1999). In such systems, flow behaviour affects the entire life of the product, including filling, mixing, packaging, removal from the container and defines the *in vivo* behaviour (Lee et al., 2009). In general, formulations with high viscosity and thixotropic properties are desirable, i.e. showing high consistency at rest, continuous decrease of viscosity with time when stress is applied and subsequent recovery of viscosity in time when the stress is discontinued (Mewis and Wagner, 2009). Peloids shows these rheological features, as they are concentrated clay suspensions resulting in structured gels (Viseras et al., 2006, 2007; Rebelo et al., 2011b). Clay gelling structures come from the aggregation of clay minerals particles by different mechanisms mainly depending on the type of clay minerals dispersed, pH and ionic strength (Lagaly, 2006). Clay mineral powders are constituted by single mineral particles (assembly of clay mineral layers), aggregates (assembly of particles) and assembly of aggregates (Bergaya and Lagaly, 2006). Traditionally, peloids were prepared with common clays, mostly consisting of mixtures of smectites, illite and kaolinite, but also including carbonates, quartz and other minerals in various proportions. Frequently, peloids need to be heated before being applied, because their therapeutic effects mainly depend on their capacity to transfer heat slowly (low cooling rates). It has been demonstrated that the use of almost pure phyllosilicates (main mineral > 90%) gave rise to systems with better thermal performance in comparison with common mixtures (Legido et al., 2007). Therapeutic activity of peloids is also related to the ionic composition of the liquid phase. It was suggested that peloids based on phyllosilicates with high cation exchange capacity (saponite, montmorillonite) may be enriched with ions provided by dispersion medium, showing potential crenotherapeutic activity (Carretero et al., 2007). It must be taken into account that rheological behaviour of a semisolid product can change over time, leading to inadequate formulations (Martin, 1993). These changes could be largely important in pelotherapy, since maturation of peloids implies prolonged periods of time from the interposition of the solid particles in the mineral medicinal water to the moment of their application. Moreover, during maturation peloids are mixed or remain undisturbed, depending on the specific protocols of each thermal station (Veniale et al., 2004). Peloids are therefore complex systems, whose rheological stability should be evaluated over maturation time. As therapeutic products, these suspensions must comply with a number of requirements, and in particular, they must realize quality constancy attributes when applied, including identity, purity and stability features.

Given these premises, aim of this work was to study the influence of maturation conditions (time and agitation) on physical stability of peloids prepared with laminar and fibrous clay samples suspended in a mineral medicinal water. The effects of particle-particle interactions (leading to new aggregates and changing the system properties) were followed by particle size measures and rheological characteristics. Maturation of the samples was carried out in static conditions (without agitation) and with manual stirring once a week, during a maximum period of three months.

2. Materials and methods

Two clay samples were used; Veegum[®] HV (VHV), a pharmaceutical grade magnesium aluminium silicate (Vanderbilt Ltd., USA), and sepiolite from Vicalvaro (SV) (Tolsa, SA, Spain). Both samples were fully characterized in previous works in terms of mineralogical, chemical, textural and technological properties (Viseras and Lopez-Galindo, 1999, 2000; Viseras et al., 2000, 2001a,b; Cerezo et al., 2001; Aguzzi et al., 2005). Accordingly, VHV was composed (>85% w/w) of at least four types of laminar shape minerals, each one corresponding to an intermediate mineral phase between di- (montmorillonite) and tri-(saponite) octahedral smectites, while SV is composed of fibrous particles of sepiolite as a percentage above 95% (w/w). 50.07 meq/100 g Na⁺ and 18.28 meq/100 g Ca²⁺ were the main exchangeable cations in VHV (Aguzzi et al., 2005).

Medicinal mineral water, hereafter referred as Graena water (Table 1), came from the thermal spring of Graena (Cortes y Graena, Granada, Spain), being used for several purposes, including pelotherapy with local clays. A Crison[®] pHmeter mod. Basic 20+ with 5010T and 5071 sensors was used to determine pH and conductivity, respectively. Dissolved ions were determined by specific titration procedures (Porretta, 1990). Distilled water was also used to compare with Graena water. The measured pH of distilled water was 5.5 (±0.12).

Table 1
Physicochemical characteristics of Graena water (means values \pm s.d.; $n = 3$).

pH	7.98 \pm 0.380
Conductivity (20 °C) (μ S/cm)	1729.75 \pm 235.968
Cl ⁻ (ppm)	17.75 \pm 1.775
SO ₄ ²⁻ (ppm)	1440.58 \pm 13.757
NO ₃ ⁻ (ppm)	1.00 \pm 0.000
NO ₂ ⁻ (ppm)	0.01 \pm 0.007
CO ₃ ²⁻ (ppm)	10.50 \pm 3.000
HCO ₃ ⁻ (ppm)	116.66 \pm 11.780
Ca ²⁺ (ppm)	438.88 \pm 34.092
Mg ²⁺ (ppm)	116.73 \pm 20.829
NH ₄ ⁺ (ppm)	0.14 \pm 0.121

2.1. Preparation of peloids

Clay/water suspensions were prepared by dispersing 25 g of VHV and SV powders in 75 g of distilled or Graena water, using a turbine stirrer (Ultraturrax T25, Janke and Kunkel GMBH & Co., G) at 10,000 rpm for 5 min. The resultant suspensions were stored at room temperature (25 °C) in airtight polyethylene containers, to avoid contamination, for three months without stirring (static maturation) or manually stirred by means of a glass rod performing planetary movements for 30 min every seven days (dynamic maturation). At time 0, 1, 2 and 3 months, aliquots of the suspensions were taken to be characterized. Name, composition and maturation conditions of each sample are shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Components and maturation conditions of the samples.

Clay mineral	Dispersion medium	Maturation	Peloid
VHV	Distilled water	Dynamic	VHV/Dist ⁺
		Static	VHV/Dist ⁻
	Graena water	Dynamic	VHV/Graena ⁺
		Static	VHV/Graena ⁻
SV	Distilled water	Dynamic	SV/Dist ⁺
		Static	SV/Dist ⁻
	Graena water	Dynamic	SV/Graena ⁺
		Static	SV/Graena ⁻

2.2. Water content, pH and particle size

The water content of suspensions was determined by weight loss on drying of 1 g of sample. pH was measured by using a pHmeter Crison (mod. 2001) equipped with a semisolid sensor (5053T). Particle size analysis was performed by a Coulter Counter method (Coulter Multisizer II, Coulter electronics Ltd., UK) with 50 μ m (VHV) and 140 μ m (SV) orifice tube. Prior to the analysis, a few milligrams of each sample were dispersed in isotonic NaCl (0.9% w/v) as conductive medium. Data were on line collected by means of AccuComp Windows Software for Z2 (Beckman Coulter, I) and particle volume equivalent diameters (d_{10} , d_{50} , d_{90}) were calculated. At least three replicates were performed for each test.

2.3. Rheological analysis

Rheological analysis was carried out with a Bohlin CS[®] rheometer (Bohlin Instrument Division, Metrics Group Ltd., UK) connected to a “personal computer” to set analysis parameters, process and record data. A cone/plate combination (CP 4/20) was used as measuring system. Measurements were carried out at room temperature (25 °C) after a rest time of 90 s. Rheological properties of the samples were measured in the range 70-800 s⁻¹ following a “constant rate test” procedure. This interval was selected as representative of the stress produced by technological operations and manipulation, like skin spreading (10-200 s⁻¹), manual mixing (100ñ-200 s⁻¹) and container removal (400-2000 s⁻¹) (Schott,1995).

Rheological characterization included the area of hysteresis between the flow curves obtained with increasing and decreasing shear rate, the yield point and the apparent viscosity of the samples. Six replicates were performed on each sample.

2.4. Statistical analysis

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with post hoc Sheffé test for multiple comparisons was performed using the software Siphar 4.0 (France). The comparison of two groups (t Student test) was performed with Statgraphics® 5.0 statistical package (Statistical Graphics Corporation, Rockville, MD, USA). Differences between groups were considered to be significant at a level of P less than 0.05.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Water content, pH and particle size

The influence of a possible decrease of water content should be controlled and taken into account for rheological studies. As expected, at time zero water content ranged between 73 and 76% (w/w) (Table 3). Implicit manipulation of the suspensions during maturation did not induced significant changes on water content values. Samples manually agitated showed slight reduction on water content, and therefore increase of solid fraction, related to manipulation, but these changes were in all cases <2% (w/w).

pH of the samples was in the interval 7.42-8.30 (Table 3). These values are included in the region of the isoelectric point of smectite edges (Avena and de Pauli, 1998). It is well known that house-of-cards aggregation of smectite particles requires edge/face contacts between positive charged edges and negative charged faces (van Olphen, 1977). At the measured pH interval face/face contacts should be predominant resulting in formation of three-dimensional band-type networks (Weiss and Frank, 1961; Weiss, 1962). Regarding the sepiolite peloids, at the measured pH and in a similar way to that described for palygorskite suspensions (Neaman and Singer, 2011), the magnitude of the negative surface charge is expected to be low. Consequently, van der Waals attraction predominates over electrostatic repulsion resulting in microaggregates of fibrous particles. Particle size analysis of the suspensions showed trending in aggregation states of the particles as a result of maturation. Initially, VHV suspensions showed $d_{90} \leq 12 \mu\text{m}$, $d_{50} \leq 2 \mu\text{m}$ and $d_{10} \leq 1 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 1). During maturation d_{90} did not show significant changes compared to the initial value. On the other hand, d_{50} progressively increased until $8 \mu\text{m}$ and d_{10} increased only at the end of the maturation process. This trend was observed independently of water medium (distilled or Graena water) or maturation conditions (dynamic or static). It must be remarked that the studied systems were very concentrated suspensions and complete swelling of smectite particles in concentrated suspensions requires long period of time (Lapides and Yariv, 2004). Therefore, long maturation time probably induced dimension increase of the aggregates, but also their interaction with individual swelled particles and consequently the number of individual particles decreased, to be less of 10% after three months of maturation. It is well known that ionic strength induces electrostatic changes on the aggregation states of very dilute smectite dispersions ($\leq 1\text{-}2\%$ w/v) (Lagaly, 2006). Accordingly, the aggregation behaviour of distilled and Graena suspensions should be clearly different, but it was not the case. It may be assumed that the high particle concentration (25% w/w of solids) reduced their mobility, even when the thickness of the double diffuse layer around the particles decreased as a result of higher ionic concentration (Graena water). Subsequently, the ratio of clay to water in the studied systems overwhelms the ionic content of the Graena water (Table 1). The relative importance of solid fraction in electrokinetic behaviour and aggregation states of these concentrated clay minerals suspensions ($\geq 25\%$, w/w) has produced some controversy in the last years. An increase of clay fraction in saponite and montmorillonite matured in seawater was explained as a result of exchange of Ca^{2+} for Na^+ (Carretero et al., 2007). On the other hand, in other works it was found that maturation of saponite and kaolinite in bidistilled and sulphate mineral water increased the size of particle aggregates and the connexions between them, resulting in enlarged pores (Gámiz et al., 2009). Probably, as suggested by Tateo et al. (2011), after measuring grain size distributions trends on different clays matured in sulphate mineral water, “case by case” studies are needed to describe the behaviour of these systems. In

our opinion, the high concentration of solids in these systems (peloids) greatly determines their behaviour. Even in much more diluted systems, it has been observed the influence of solid concentration on the aggregation state and properties of clay suspensions (Lapides and Yariv, 2004).

Table 3
Water content and pH of the samples (mean values \pm s.e.; n=3).

Peloid	Water content (w/w %)				pH (20 °C)			
	Time zero	One month	Two months	Three months	Time zero	One month	Two months	Three months
VHV/Dist ⁺	74.30 \pm 0.071	72.97 \pm 0.145	72.84 \pm 0.855	72.67 \pm 1.103	8.14 \pm 0.303	7.89 \pm 0.032	7.83 \pm 0.081	7.85 \pm 0.234
VHV/Dist ⁻	75.74 \pm 0.227	75.76 \pm 0.155	75.73 \pm 0.029	75.07 \pm 0.032	8.08 \pm 0.303	8.06 \pm 0.026	8.02 \pm 0.130	7.92 \pm 0.169
VHV/Graena ⁺	73.85 \pm 0.816	72.74 \pm 0.213	72.48 \pm 0.626	72.37 \pm 0.947	7.55 \pm 0.303	7.44 \pm 0.144	7.47 \pm 0.090	7.42 \pm 0.148
VHV/Graena ⁻	74.20 \pm 0.727	73.87 \pm 0.243	73.36 \pm 0.100	73.44 \pm 0.804	7.79 \pm 0.303	7.84 \pm 0.070	8.08 \pm 0.044	7.98 \pm 0.090
SV/Dist ⁺	74.40 \pm 0.238	72.48 \pm 1.900	72.57 \pm 1.292	72.59 \pm 1.717	8.30 \pm 0.244	8.09 \pm 0.049	7.88 \pm 0.032	8.08 \pm 0.092
SV/Dist ⁻	74.55 \pm 0.501	73.71 \pm 0.920	73.38 \pm 2.135	72.95 \pm 1.700	8.20 \pm 0.026	8.16 \pm 0.118	8.15 \pm 0.136	8.10 \pm 0.474
SV/Graena ⁺	74.24 \pm 0.803	73.28 \pm 0.903	72.87 \pm 1.279	72.56 \pm 0.989	7.85 \pm 0.061	7.89 \pm 0.030	7.87 \pm 0.167	7.82 \pm 0.029
SV/Graena ⁻	74.63 \pm 0.062	73.81 \pm 0.347	73.49 \pm 0.806	73.01 \pm 0.610	7.87 \pm 0.353	7.86 \pm 0.076	7.81 \pm 0.093	7.79 \pm 0.031

Particle aggregates in SV suspensions (Fig. 2) showed average diameter at time zero ranging from 4 μ m (d_{10}) to 40 μ m (d_{90}), approximately. As a result of maturation, significant differences in statistical diameters (compared to time zero) were only observed in periodically shaken suspensions. In particular, d_{10} values increased from 4 to 6 μ m, and d_{50} from 12 μ m to approximately 18 μ m at the end of maturation. It can be hypothesized that sample agitation led to collisions between particles and small aggregates, promoting their aggregation. Differences between laminar and fibrous dispersions may be explained on the basis of their aggregation mechanisms (Viseras et al., 1999, 2001b). Rod-like (fibrous) sepiolite particles tend to align the major axis in aggregates, and low shearing promotes sticking of new particles (or aggregates), whereas aggregates of disc-like (laminar) smectite particles do not have a preferential orientation being structurally independent from hydrodynamic effects due to low agitation.

3.2. Rheological properties

The studied peloids showed, whatever the maturation time and dispersion medium, typical non-Newtonian viscoplastic (i.e. pseudoplastic with yield points) flow curves, as expected with concentrated suspensions of flocculated clay particles (van Olphen, 1977). As representative example, flow curves (shear stress vs. shear flow) at time zero are shown in Fig. 3, in which the progressive decline in shear stress slope as shear rate increased is characteristic of pseudoplastic systems, that can be accurately described by the Bingham model (Güven, 1992). Laminar particle gels (VHV) showed spur peaks (typical of very concentrated suspensions (Barry, 1974)) and thixotropic behaviour whereas rod-like particle gels (SV) did not show any initial spur and were rheopectic. In thixotropic VHV peloids, application of shear rate determined a reversible rupture of the internal network, the recovery of which gradually went on once the applied stress was removed or reduced. Negative thixotropy observed in SV peloids represents a reversible increase, rather than a decrease, of the consistency of the sample in the curve of return. It could be said that the structure of negative thixotropic materials is formed during the shear and vice versa weakens when the stress stops. Orientation of the fibres during the flow align them respect to their major axis, increasing their contact area and resulting in an augment of required energy to flow in the return curve of the rheogram. From the flow curves, it was possible to obtain the apparent viscosities (at 350 s^{-1}), yield values (characteristic value of shear stress necessary to break the attractions between adjacent particles, representative of the flow resistance of the formed gel) and hysteresis area (correlated to thixotropy). Yield values of SV were calculated according to the Bingham model as the intercept of the linear portion of the flow curve with the stress axis. In the case of VHV, yield stresses were directly obtained from the shear stress value corresponding to the experimental spur point (Barry, 1974). The influence of maturation process in apparent viscosities and yield points of the studied gels are shown in Table 4. Maturation in laminar gels resulted in significant increase of apparent viscosity values, independently from agitation conditions. In particular, after three months of maturation the level of significance (with respect to time zero) was 99.9% in all cases ($P < 0.001$, 1-way ANOVA, post hoc Scheffé test, "Simple Contrast between Means"). Fibrous gels only showed minor increases of apparent viscosities in samples that had been matured with agitation.

Changes of yield values followed the same pattern that apparent viscosities. These results indicated that maturation increased the degree of structure of the laminar systems (as a result of delamination and swelling). Yield values in systems constituted by flocculated particles in concentrated suspensions are associated to attractions between adjacent particles established by virtue of van der Waals forces, which must be broken before the material can start to flow. In the case of VHV, these links were particularly intense, and flow curves showed spurs typical of structured systems with high flow resistance (Barry, 1974; Martin, 1993; Mewis and Wagner, 2009).

Regarding time-dependent characteristics of the gels, area of hysteresis of VHV peloids increased with progressing maturation time (Fig. 4). These results suggested that samples became more structured, in line with the observed increase in apparent viscosities and yield values. Fibrous peloids of SV showed negative thixotropy, as it has been also described for aqueous suspensions of palygorskite (Neaman and Singer, 2000). It has been hypothesized that, similarly to what is observed in a system subjected to mechanical stirring, shearing may increase the frequency of collision between suspended particles, promoting their aggregation and the formation of a three-dimensional system structured (Martin, 1993; Barnes, 1997; Mewis and Wagner, 2009). When the flow stops, the structure weakens and the system gradually recovers to its initial state. This hypothesis agrees with the theory that attributes the formation of gels of sepiolite mainly to hydrodynamic factors and not to electrostatic interactions (Viseras et al., 1999, 2001b; López-Galindo et al., 2011). In the case of dynamic maturation, the time dependent behaviour of SV gels, initially anti-thixotropic, changed significantly, to become thixotropic after 2-3 months of maturation (Fig. 4). Probably, the periodic agitation of the samples, by promoting the assembly of fibres, produced a stable structured system over time, capable of manifesting a thixotropic behaviour in flow conditions. To support this idea, the observed time-dependent behaviour changes concurred with high increases in yield point values (Table 4) observed at 2-3 months of maturation on periodic agitated samples.

Fig. 1. Statistical diameters of VHV suspensions (mean values \pm s.e.; $n = 3-6$).

Fig. 2. Statistical diameters of SV suspensions (mean values \pm s.e.; $n = 3-6$).

Table 4
Apparent viscosities (Pa s; 350 s⁻¹; 25 °C) and yield values (Pa) of the samples (mean values ± s.e.; n = 6).

Maturation time (months)	Viscosity	Yield value	Viscosity	Yield value	Viscosity	Yield value	Viscosity	Yield value
	VHV/Dist ⁺		VHV/Dist ⁻		VHV/Graena ⁺		VHV/Graena ⁻	
0	4.04 ± 0.060	2037 ± 125.0	3.78 ± 0.260	2009 ± 223.4	4.18 ± 0.180	2177 ± 170.0	4.01 ± 0.145	2065 ± 95.0
1	6.67 ± 0.493	2860 ± 80.0	6.46 ± 0.288	2558 ± 173.2	6.29 ± 0.250	2658 ± 67.4	5.11 ± 0.137	2464 ± 178.1
2	7.45 ± 0.257	3005 ± 52.0	7.28 ± 0.352	2970 ± 74.0	6.70 ± 0.609	3120 ± 147.0	6.80 ± 0.045	2004 ± 151.0
3	8.00 ± 0.200	3108 ± 256.4	7.60 ± 0.479	3050 ± 87.2	8.04 ± 0.465	3450 ± 99.2	7.77 ± 0.140	2560 ± 88.2

Maturation time (months)	Viscosity	Yield value	Viscosity	Yield value	Viscosity	Yield value	Viscosity	Yield value
	SV/Dist ⁺		SV/Dist ⁻		SV/Graena ⁺		SV/Graena ⁻	
0	2.46 ± 0.074	160 ± 18.4	2.48 ± 0.058	218 ± 19.4	2.60 ± 0.104	151 ± 24.6	2.38 ± 0.051	209 ± 15.2
1	2.78 ± 0.131	190 ± 12.7	2.54 ± 0.212	189 ± 28.7	3.25 ± 0.081	211 ± 26.3	2.77 ± 0.199	222 ± 19.1
2	3.32 ± 0.037	1165 ± 24.2	3.11 ± 0.492	225 ± 21.5	3.16 ± 0.001	336 ± 11.4	2.69 ± 0.067	232 ± 32.5
3	3.41 ± 0.008	1208 ± 43.5	2.83 ± 0.094	215 ± 18.2	3.40 ± 0.238	957 ± 25.9	3.23 ± 0.084	231 ± 25.6

4. Conclusions

Particle and aggregate sizes, as well as rheological properties of concentrated suspension of laminar and fibrous clay mineral particles depended on the networking mechanisms; laminar clay gels, at the studied pH, were made by “face–face” interactions between individual particles resulting in band-type networks, whereas fibrous clay gels were formed by hydrodynamic interparticle contacts. Maturation time increased dimensions of laminar aggregates, whereas fibrous aggregates only enlarged under agitation. Rheological properties of these systems resulted from their aggregation states; apparent viscosities and yield points increased with particle aggregation. Consequently, maturation of clay suspensions resulted in improved rheological properties, as peloids should easily flow when applied and possess sufficient consistency at rest. In the case of laminar clay suspensions the systems became more structured with time of maturation, whereas for fibrous clay systems it was also necessary to agitate the suspensions periodically during maturation process to obtain thixotropic gels. The observed changes in the properties of the systems as a result of maturation were independent from the water type (distilled or Graena). Consequently, as concern the studied properties, the physical stability of the suspensions was not impaired by the specific composition of the Graena medicinal water.

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Fig. 3. Flow curves of VHV and SV suspensions obtained at time zero and static maturation. Up: VHV; down: SV (mean values \pm s.e.; n = 6).

Fig. 4. Area of hysteresis of the samples. Up: VHV; down: SV (mean values \pm s.e.; n = 6).

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